

Orbital Order-Disorder Transition in Doped Perovskite Manganites: Influence of Intrinsic Octahedral-Site Distortion

Partha Sarathi Mondal*¹ and Dipten Bhattacharya²

¹National Institute of Foundry and Forge Technology, Hatia, Ranchi, India

²Central Glass and Ceramic Research Institute-CSIR, Kolkata, India

*E-mail: psm.nift@gov.in and Mob:9536912014

Abstract

The orbital order-disorder transition temperature (T_{OO}) versus tolerance factor (t) plot switches from monotonic to non-monotonic beyond a doping level (x) ~ 10 atom% in a family of $R_{1-x}A_xMnO_3$ systems ($R = La, Pr, Nd$; $A = Ca, Sr$; $x = 0.0-0.2$). T_{OO} reaches maximum at a ‘doping-dependent’ critical tolerance factor $t_c(x)$ at which the orthorhombic distortion (D) also maximizes. Such an observation reflects influence of charge carriers on both ‘intrinsic’ octahedral-site distortion itself and its bias on the orbital order in doped perovskite manganites and, thus, deviation from what has been observed in undoped $RMnO_3$, $RTiO_3$, and RVO_3 systems where maximization of T_{OO} and D takes place at a universal tolerance factor or R-site ion size [1-3].

Manganite, Orbital order, Strongly correlated electron system, Tolerance factor

References

- [1] M. De Raychaudhury, E. Pavarini, and O. K. Andersen, Phys. Rev. Lett. **99**, 126402 (2007)
- [2] E. Pavarini, E. Koch, and A. I. Lichtenstein, Phys. Rev. Lett. **101**, 266405 (2008)
- [3] Eva Pavarini and Erik Koch, Phys. Rev. Lett. **104**, 086402 (2010)